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The Effect of Red Onion Solution (*Allium cepa* L.) on Viability and Vigor of Soybean Seeds (*Glycine max* L. Merrill)

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Abstract:

This research was conducted to determine the effect of soaking and the best concentration of shallot solution on the viability and vigor of the Anjasmoro variety soybean seeds which have experienced decline. This research was carried out during December - January 2023. Located at the Laboratory of the Center for Supervision and Certification of Food Plant and Horticultural Seeds (BPSTPH) South Kalimantan Province. The research was carried out using a one-factor Completely Randomized Design (CRD) method with five treatments and four replications to obtain 20 experimental units. Each experimental unit consists of 3 subsamples and the seeds required for each experimental unit are 50 seeds. The treatments that will be applied are as follows: K0 (Control): 0% concentration of shallot solution, K1: 10% shallot solution, K2: 15% shallot solution, K3: 20% shallot solution and K4: 25% shallot solution. The results showed that the soybean seed invigoration treatment with concentrations of 10%, 15%, 20% and 25% had no real effect on increasing germination power, maximum growth potential, growth speed, growth simultaneity and normal dry weight of the sprouts, but had a significant effect on seed vigor in vigor index benchmark. Seed invigoration in shallot solution with a concentration of 25% has a significant effect on seed vigor in the vigor index parameter

Keywords: Deterioration of seeds; Soybeans; Invigoration; Onions

Introduction

Soybean (*Glycine max*) is one of the most popular food crops among the people of Indonesia because of its high nutritional value. This plant is grown mainly for various culinary purposes such as making tofu, tempeh, soy sauce, and so on. Soybeans contain B vitamins, protein (40%), oils (20%), carbohydrates (35%), and ash (5%). Although it does not contain vitamin B12 and vitamin C, soybeans remain a superior source of vitamin B compared to other grain products (Krisnawati, 2017).

According to the Center for Agricultural Data and Information Systems (2020), the average national soybean production in 2015-2019 grew negative 15.54% per year. Meanwhile, soybean needs for industry are around 3.06 million tons. The need for domestic soybeans is very high but most of them are still imported soybeans. Meanwhile, soybean production in South Kalimantan in 2018-2021 showed a significant decline, soybean production in 2018 was 25,177 tons, then in 2019 it was 4,698 tons, in 2020 it was 2,295 tons, then in 2021 it was 852 tons (Food Crops and Horticulture Office of South Kalimantan Province, 2022).

The comparison between the needs and availability of domestic soybeans shows that domestic soybean production has not been able to meet the needs. People's need for soybeans continues to increase along with the increase in population every year. So it must be balanced with an increase in production to meet these needs. The use of quality seeds will produce healthy plants so that plants are able to produce more optimally.

As an effort to increase domestic consumption, soybean production needs to be increased, of course, by using quality seeds (Agung & Rahayu, 2004).

The provision of soybean seeds has been carried out by farmers before the growing season so that the seeds must first be stored before planting. Seeds that are stored for too long can cause seed quality to decrease so that seeds regress (Suchyono, 2014). Deterioration in seed quality (deterioration) can have an indirect impact on crop production. Deterioration in seed quality begins when the seeds ripen physiologically. Physiological deterioration of seeds is characterized by decreased viability and vigor of seeds. The physiological level of seed ripeness can also affect seed growth potential (Farida, 2018).

Seed invigoration can be done using growth regulators or known as ZPT (Sutariati and Madiki, 2014). Seed invigoration using ZPT is usually done by soaking the seeds in ZPT solution. The use of ZPT can increase the remodeling activity of organic matter in seeds so that food reserves for germination are available and can be used for embryonic development. In addition, embryos can more quickly utilize germination supporting factors such as water and oxygen (Adelina and Maemunah, 2009).

Shallots are thought to be used as growth regulators. According to Darajat *et al.*, (2015), onion extract (*Allium cepa* L.) a concentration of 10% is able to increase the percentage of germination, growing speed, hypocotyledonous length and root length of cocoa seeds (*Theobroma cacao* L.). According to Yanti (2020), invigorasi rice seeds with onion solution with a concentration of 15% has a real effect on the quality of rice seeds on the parameters of germination, coarseness and maximum growth potential. Lestari *et al.*, (2020) concluded that soaking Kaba variety soybean seeds with ZPT doses of onion extract (40%, 60%, 100%) increased germination value, vigor index, maximum growing potential, seed growing speed, plant height and number of leaves compared to control (0%).

Based on this background, a study was conducted to determine the effect of treatment of several onion solution concentrations of less than 40% on the viability and vigor of seeds to the delay (*Glycine max* L. Merrill) of the Anjasmoro variety that has regressed.

Materials and Methods

This research was conducted for two months, namely from December 2022 –January 2023. Located in the Laboratory of the Center for Supervision and Certification of Food and Horticultural Crop Seeds (BPSTPH) of South Kalimantan Province. The materials used in this study were Anjasmoro variety soybean seeds obtained from UPBS Balitkabi Malang, shallots, aquades, water, CD paper, label paper, clear plastic, brown envelopes and the tools used in this study were work stationery, thermometers, germinators, ovens, hand sprayers, tweezers, analytical scales, filters, measuring cups, blenders, 1000 mL plastic jars, funnels, tray, knife, camera.

This study used a one-factor Complete Randomized Design (RAL) with five treatments and four repeats so that 20 experimental units were obtained. The treatment used is soaking soybean seeds at several concentrations of onion solution as follows: K0 (control): Shallot solution 0% concentration, K1: 10% onion solution, K2: 15% onion solution, K3: 20% onion solution and K4: 25% onion solution. Each experimental unit consists of 3 sub-samples and the seeds needed for each experimental unit are 50 grains.

The implementation of the research includes the preparation of soybean seeds that have been stored for more than 4 months, making a solution of onion stock using 200 grams of shallots that have been washed and dried by air then mashed using a blender by adding 500 mL of aquades (Yanti, 2020). Then poured into jars, let stand for 10 minutes and then filtered and obtained stocks of onion solution with a concentration of 100%. Soaking of seeds is carried out on onion solution according to the required concentration for 3 hours. After that, the seeds were germinated on opaque paper substrates as many as 50 seeds on each substrate by the rolled paper test method established in plastic (UKDdp). All labeled rolls are then arranged inside the germinator. Observations were made on tollak measure germination power (DB), maximum growth potential (PTM, seed growing speed (KcT), vigor index (IV), coarseness of growth (KsT) and dry weight of normal sprouts (BKKN). The data from this study was tested for homogeneity using the Bartlett variety, then a variety analysis (ANOVA) was carried out using Microsoft Excel. If the analyzed data has a real effect ($P \leq 0.05$), then a DMRT test is carried out at the level of α 5%.

Results and Discussion

Germination

The results of variety analysis showed that soaking treatment of soybean seeds in onion solution had no real effect on germination parameters. The average germination of seeds can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 1. The average germination of soybean seeds due to soaking treatment using onion solution.

The results of variety analysis showed that invigoration treatment using onion solution with concentrations of 10%, 15%, 20% and 25% has not been able to significantly increase the germination of Anjasmoro variety soybean seeds that have been stored for more than 4 months. The highest average germination of soybean seeds is shown by soaking treatment using onion solution with a concentration of 25% (K4) with a germination power of 77%. This germination rate is still relatively low, because according to the Director General of Food Crops (2009), the passing standard for soybean seed certification is to have a germination power of >80%.

The low germination of seeds from all treatments shows that seed soaking treatment using onion solutions of 10%, 15%, 20% and 25% concentrations has not been able to significantly increase the germination of soybean seeds of the Anjasmoro variety that has been stored for more than 4 months and has experienced seed deterioration.

This decrease in germination is because the shelf life of the seeds is more than 4 months since the initial testing and the moisture content of the seeds has increased. According to Nurmauli (2010), the stored seeds have a high initial moisture content so that by soaking the seeds, the rate of imbibition is not controlled by the cell membrane which causes the seed moisture content to be higher. Cell membranes that absorb water too high will interfere with and inhibit seed metabolic activity so that it can produce germination, coarseness of germination, and low dry weight of sprouts.

Low germination is also thought to be influenced by increased seed moisture content due to long storage. It is known that the moisture content on the label is 8.7%, then in the initial test the moisture content of the seeds is 9.8%, increasing by 1.1% after being stored for more than 4 months. In line with Justice and Bass (1994) who stated that seed germination during storage is strongly influenced by seed moisture content, temperature, room relative humidity, and initial viability of seeds before storage.

Soaking using onion extract at a concentration of 25% gave the highest yield of 77%, but was not significantly different from all other soaking concentration treatments. The lowest germination yield is found in soaking 15% onion solution, which is 66%. The increase in germination value along with the increase in the concentration of onion solution in soaking is thought to be due to the hormone content in shallots that support increased germination. But the concentration treatment given (10%, 15%, 20%, 25%) is still too low. Marfirani *et al.*, (2014), stated that shallots (*Allium cepa* L.) contain ZPT auxin and gibberellin so that they can be used as one of the natural growth regulators. Every plant has hormones to stimulate

germination, but the hormones in the seeds are small so they need to be added so that seed growth will be faster and better.

Maximum Growth Potential

The results of the variety analysis showed that the soaking treatment of onion solution had no real effect on the maximum growth potential. The average maximum growing potential of seeds can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 2. The average maximum growth potential of soybean seeds due to soaking treatment using onion solution.

Soybean seed invigoration treatment using onion solution with concentrations of 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25% did not have a noticeable effect on the maximum growing potential of Anjasmoro variety soybean seeds. All treatments on the maximum growth potential benchmark did not show a significantly different effect, because the evaluation for maximum growth potential of seeds was only seen in sprouted seeds, even though the seeds grew into normal and abnormal sprouts.

This is thought to be because endogenous hormones in soybean seeds are sufficient for germination. So that the application of natural ZPT through soaking soybean seeds in onion solution with concentrations of 10%, 15%, 20% and 25% does not have a real effect on the sprout growth process for maximum growth potential.

Seed soaking treatment in onion solution has not had a noticeable effect on the parameters of maximum growth potential, allegedly because the seeds already have sufficient growth hormone. As Salisbury and Ross (1995) state, states that plants have a control mechanism for giving auxin from outside so that if the synthesized hormone is sufficient to support the metabolic process, the administration of growth regulators from outside will not affect growth. Gardner *et al.*, (1991) in Subantoro & Prabowo (2013) stated that endogenous auxin hormones can be produced by plants themselves.

The germination process is not only influenced by the presence of endogenous hormones in seeds, germination is also influenced by factors of physiological abilities of seeds to the environment. Farida (2018) stated that the level of seed maturity physiologically affects the potential for seed growth. Rofik & Muniarti (2008), added that maximum growth potential is influenced by environmental factors such as humidity, temperature, light as well as internal factors in the form of seed type and oxygen tissue metabolism in influencing germination.

Vigor Index

The results of the variety analysis show that soaking soybean seeds has a significant effect on the vigour of soybean seeds on the vigor index benchmark. The average vigor index of seeds can be seen in the following figure.

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Figure 3. Average Vigor Index of soybean seeds due to soaking treatment using onion solution. The same letter shows that the treatment is not significantly different based on the 5% DMRT.

Seed soaking treatment using onion solution with a concentration of 25% (K4) showed the highest value of 50.5%, then the lowest at a concentration of 10% (K1) which was 40.5%. The high vigor index in K4 treatment is thought to be because the concentration of onion solution used, which is 25%, is able to produce hormones that stimulate the germination of soybean seeds to grow, producing normal and strong sprouts higher than 100% aqueous treatment (K1) and soaking in onion solution concentrations of 10%, 15%, and 20%. The vigor index is used to determine the ability of seeds to grow normally, strong and have a normal germination structure. Marfirani *et al.*, (2014), stated that shallots (*Allium cepa* L.) contain ZPT auxin and gibberellin so that they can be used as one of the natural growth regulators. Research by Tini *et al.*, (2022), states that onion bulbs contain IAA 251.76 ppm; kinetin 75.54 ppm; Zeatin 23.77 ppm; and GA₃ 594.12 ppm. Shallot bulbs have the highest GA₃ content compared to banana weevils (104.12 ppm), Moringa leaves (417.88 ppm), sweet corn kernels (269.75 ppm) and green bean sprouts (371.56 ppm). Every plant has hormones to stimulate germination, but the hormones in the seeds are small so they need to be added so that seed growth will be faster and better.

Seed vigor is more burdensome on seed strength, the ability of seeds to produce strong roots and shoots under unfavorable conditions (suboptimum) and free from microorganism attack. A high vigor index can be obtained by maintaining environmental conditions during storage. Yuniarti *et al.*, (2014) stated that seed vigor is influenced by various factors ranging from when the seeds are still in the parent plant to harvesting, processing, transportation and before planting.

Growing Speed

The results of variety analysis showed that seed soaking treatment using onion solution had no real effect on the growth speed benchmark. Analysis of the variety of growing speed due to soaking treatment using onion solution can be seen in the following figure.

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Figure 4. The average growth speed of soybean seeds due to soaking treatment using onion solution.

Seed soaking treatment using onion solution with different concentrations did not show a real different effect. Although the 100% aqueous soaking treatment (K0) has the highest average speed value compared to the soaking treatment with onion solution. This is thought to be due to the germination media factor that has previously been moistened using water, but still does not support the germination process because the hormones in the germination process have not been optimal. This is in accordance with the opinion of Darajat *et al.* (2019), that every plant has hormones to stimulate germination, but still in small amounts so it needs to be added for seed growth. The concentration of ZPT in the treatment will affect the amount and speed of absorption that occurs in seeds, so that it will affect the speed of germination, germination and fertility of seeds.

A decrease in the average value of germination speed indicates that the seeds experience a decrease in germination during the storage process followed by an increase in the percentage of moisture content. Roberts (1972) in Kolo and Tefa (2016) states that this is a biological symptom experienced by seeds during storage. One of the biological processes experienced by seeds during storage is the metabolic process, especially the respiration process associated with the deterioration process of seed quality. Deterioration of seed quality during storage can occur if food reserves for embryonic growth are reduced or depleted due to the metabolic process of respiration.

The results of research by Hartawan *et al.*, (2011) showed that the growing speed of soybean seeds after being stored for 90 days at room temperature was related to the percentage of food reserves and other seed quality. Seed protein content affects the speed of germination after being stored for 90 days. This study shows that seeds require food reserves, especially protein, in determining the quality of seeds during storage. Seeds with 100% aqueous treatment (K0) showed the highest average speed but did not differ significantly from other concentration treatments. This is suspected because the paper used as a medium is too wet, as a result the seeds experience excess water absorption so that the application of onion solutions with different concentrations has not shown a noticeable influence on the parameters of seed growing speed. According to Garderr *et al* (1991) in Lubis, *et al.*, (2018) stated that the germination process begins with water absorption by seeds and hydration from protoplasm then enzyme activation and digestion, transport of hydrolyzed molecules to the embryonic shaft, increased respiration and assimilation, initiation of cell division and enlargement and embryo emergence.

Simultaneous Growing

The results of the variety analysis showed that seed soaking treatment in onion solution with different concentrations had no real effect on the benchmark of seed growth coarseness. Analysis of the variety of cohesiveness of growing soybean seeds can be seen in the following figure.

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Figure 5. The average coarseness of soybean seeds grows due to soaking treatment using onion solution.

The highest growth coarseness was shown by seed soaking treatment in onion solution with a concentration of 15% (K2) higher by 7% compared to 100% aqueous treatment (K0), while for the lowest yield shown in 100% aqueous soaking (K0) by 56%. Soybean seed soaking treatment with onion solutions of 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25% concentrations did not differ markedly from controls. This is in line with the statement of Sadjad *et al*, (1999) stating that seeds can grow simultaneously if the viability and vigor of seeds after storage are still good so that seeds are able to adapt to environmental conditions after the seeds are stored at room temperature. The cohesiveness of growing good seeds ranges from 40% - 70%.

Soybean seed soaking that has regressed in onion solution at different concentrations showed no real effect, although soaking using shallots with different concentrations showed higher numbers compared to soaking without using onion solution (K0) and soaking concentration of 15% (K2) showed the highest number of 63%. This is thought to be because the ZPT content in shallots supports to increase the coarseness of growing in soybean seeds. Yanti's research (2020), states that the concentration of 15% onion solution has been able to show the cohesiveness of growing rice seeds with the highest average percentage of 45.5%.

Normal Sprout Dry Weight

The results of variety analysis showed that seed soaking treatment using onion solution had no real effect on the viability of soybean seeds on the normal sprout dry weight benchmark (BKKN). Analysis of the variety of dry weight of normal sprouts of soybean seeds can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 6. The dry weight of normal sprouts of soybean seeds due to soaking treatment using onion solution.

The research findings indicate that the highest normal seedling dry weight was observed in soybean seed immersion treatment in a 20% red onion solution (K3), which was 3.94%. Conversely, the lowest normal

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seedling dry weight of soybean seeds was shown in the seed immersion treatment with 100% aquadest concentration (K0), at 3.24%. Normal seedling dry weight serves as one of the indicators of potential seed viability, depicting the amount of available food reserves. Therefore, under suitable environmental conditions, it could grow and develop well (Sadjad et al., 1999).

The high normal seedling dry weight signifies efficient utilization of food reserves within the seeds. The results indicate that although immersion in red onion solution didn't exhibit a significant difference in this parameter, the use of red onion resulted in a higher dry weight compared to 100% aquadest immersion (K0). This is presumed to be due to the hormonal influence of the red onion solution, aiding in more efficient utilization of food reserves by the seeds. Nurussintani et al. (2012) further suggest that the increased accumulation of dry weight is due to high-vigor seeds capable of rapidly forming and translocating raw materials to the embryo axis. Efficient utilization of food reserves within the seeds is depicted by the high dry weight.

Sutopo (2004) states that seed weight influences growth rate and production since seed weight determines the size of the seedling at the onset and the plant's weight during harvest. Efficient utilization of food reserves within the seeds is indicated by a high dry weight. According to Tarigan et al. (2017), red onion extract contains natural auxins and rhizokalin, which can trigger root formation.

Conclusion

The invigoration treatment on Anjasmoro soybean seeds using red onion solutions at concentrations of 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25% did not significantly impact germination rate, maximum growth potential, growth speed, uniformity of growth, and normal seedling dry weight. However, it did have a significant effect on seed vigor based on the vigor index. The 25% concentration of the red onion solution exhibited the most significant impact on the seed vigor index during the immersion treatment with red onion solutions. Further research is needed on the hormone concentrations in red onions as growth regulators and subsequent studies using different mediums.

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